

THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *Today, interest in the concept of the digital economy has grown significantly due to significant changes that have occurred in society and the economy. This article describes reforms aimed at developing the digital economy in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *Digital infrastructure, infrastructure, smart contract, crypto asset, consulting, blockchain, smart contract, emission, crowdfunding.*

Annotatsiya : *Bugungi kunda raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasiga bo'lgan qiziqish jamiyat va iqtisodiyotda ro'y bergan jiddiy o'zgarishlar tufayli sezilarli darajada o'sdi. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan islohotlar o'rin olgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Raqamli infratuzilma, infratuzilma, smart-kontrakt, kripto-aktiv, konsalting, blokcheyn, smart-kontrakt, emissiya, kraud-fanding.*

Of course, we know very well that the formation of a digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, large financial and labor resources. However, no matter how difficult it is, if we don't start today, then when?! Tomorrow will be too late. Therefore, an active transition to the digital economy will be one of our main priorities in the next 5 years.

Sh.M.Mirziyoyev

The digital economy is developing in Uzbekistan, as in other countries of the world. The adoption of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated July 3, 2018 No. PQ-3832, identified the most important development tasks, including the following:

- implementation of activities in the field of circulation of crypto assets, including mining technologies, smart contracts, consulting, emission, exchange, storage, distribution, management, insurance, crowdfunding (collective financing) in order to diversify various forms of investment. and entrepreneurial activity;

- training qualified personnel with practical work skills, well versed in modern information and communication technologies in the development and use of blockchain technologies, as well as attracting highly qualified foreign specialists;

- comprehensive development of cooperation with international and foreign organizations in the field of activities on crypto-assets and blockchain technologies, as well as the creation of the necessary legal framework taking into account advanced foreign experience;

- ensure close cooperation between government agencies and business entities in the field of introducing innovative ideas, technologies and developments for the further development of the digital economy.

It should be noted that some elements of the digital economy are already successfully operating in the life of our country. In particular, with the advent of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to the leadership of Uzbekistan in 2016, the economy of our republic has undergone dramatic changes. The economy has become open, dynamically developing, innovative, in accordance with the goals of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, as well as the creation of additional conditions for the development of the digital economy, the following have been adopted:

- Resolution No. PQ-3832 of July 3, 2018 “On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan”[1].

- Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for further modernization of digital infrastructure in order to develop the digital economy” dated November 21, 2018 PQ – No. 4022[2].

- PQ-3832 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 07/03/03 “On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan” and blockchain with practical skills in using modern information and communication technologies. Development of technologies and training of qualified personnel in the field of their use.

In accordance with the tasks defined in the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017 - 2021 in the “Year of Development of Science, Education and Digital Economy” and modern information on sectors of the economy and the public administration system. In order to further increase the competitiveness of the republic’s economy through the widespread introduction of digital technologies and the expansion of telecommunication networks, the following tasks have been identified as additional tasks for the further development of the digital economy and e-government:

- By 2023, subject to doubling the share of the digital economy in the country’s gross domestic product, including the introduction of a complex of information systems in production management, the widespread use of software products in financial and economic reporting, as well as automation of technological processes, is carried out intensively;

- Complete modernization of the country's digital infrastructure in 2020-2021 in order to connect all healthcare institutions, schools and preschool institutions, as well as villages and neighborhoods to high-speed Internet and improve the quality of communication services to create and provide access to modern telecommunications services in all regions;

- Creation and integration of state information systems and resources, unification of information in state databases, as well as optimization and regulation of procedures for the provision of public services, suggesting increasing the share of electronic public services to 60 percent by 2022;

- development of "digital entrepreneurship" through the production of software products and the creation of technological platforms; by 2023, the volume of services in this area should triple, and their exports should reach \$100 million;

- widespread introduction of digital technologies at all stages of the education system and increasing the level of digital knowledge necessary for the modern economy, improving educational infrastructure, as well as, as part of the implementation of the "Five Initiatives" project, digital knowledge in all regions of the republic until 2022, the opening of training centers.

In conclusion, it should be said that the qualitative development of economic sectors, the social sphere and the public administration system in the current period of human development and in the near future is directly related to the widespread introduction of digital technologies. Our country's development prospects also depend on the development of the digital economy and the level of digital inclusion. If the goals of the digital economy are realized, great practical results will be evident in all areas, and the well-being of the population will significantly increase.

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